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Mapping out HRJs in Taiwan

D 7.6 tasks 7-8 and D.3.2 task 4 WP3

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1. Executive Summary

This memo summarizes the research questions, steps, theory, and preliminary findings of Team Taiwan from Work Package 5 (migration) over the first nine months, spanning from March to December 2023. The team conducted a comprehensive review of state reports submitted to committees of UN human rights conventions that are domesticated in Taiwan. Through this analysis, the team delineated the HRJ techniques employed by the Taiwanese government in the realm of Human Rights within the context of migration policy, marking the completion of Task 1 in WP5. The memo also elucidates how these identified techniques shape the research design and civil society engagement for the upcoming second year, encompassing Tasks 2 and 3 of WP5. Additionally, the team outlines a schedule plan for the subsequent tasks, covering Tasks 3 to 8.

2. Research question and how it relates to the task and objective of WP5

Our research question is threefold, revolving around the 'what,' 'why,' and 'so what' aspects of HRJ phenomena in Taiwan concerning migration. Firstly, we inquire about the techniques or rhetoric the Taiwanese government employs to justify regulating the entrance, exit, and stay of foreigners in Taiwan with the language of human rights. This question serves the primary purpose of completing Task 1 (mapping out state practices of HRJ) within WP5. However, it also lays the groundwork for the empirical research design (Task 2 of WP5) and the initial phase of civil society engagement (Task 3 of WP5).

Secondly, we explore why HRJ might pose particular challenges in the context of migration and why Taiwan presents a distinctive case study regarding HRJ. This question informs our analysis (Task 4 of WP5) of the data collected in Task 3 and sheds light on the second phase of civil society engagement (Task 5 of WP5).

Thirdly, we investigate the implications of HRJ for the European Union's role in establishing human rights standards beyond the EU and its relationship with third countries. In other words, even if HRJ proves problematic in the context of migration policy in Taiwan, why should the EU care? This question aids in synthesizing findings from the previous two years (Task 6 of WP5) and generating insights on migration policies (Task 8 of WP5).

3. Method

During our first nine months, we primarily focused on the first question (mapping out the Taiwanese government's HRJ on migration) through desk research. Our primary materials included Taiwan's state reports submitted to international committees of United Nations human rights conventions because they offer rich texts about how the government respond to human rights pressure from domestic civil society and international experts. We also reviewed statutes, regulations, and government press releases regarding the treatment of foreigners.

We ask the following questions to map out Taiwan's HRJ on migration:

- To whom is the government addressing? Who are the expected audiences of the government's HRJ on migration?
- What rights are at stake? Which categories of rights are prone to be undermined by HRJ?
- Who are the stakeholders or right holders?
- What techniques are used to frame HRJ ?

After identifying potential cases (see below), we then assessed their research potential based on the following criteria:

- The richness of texts in the state reports
- Practical and theoretical significance: To what extent can the case study shed light on who and what rights are prone to be affected by HRJ, and what does that tell us about the significance of HRJ on migration?
- Available research tools
- Gender significance (which enables us to contribute to WP7)

4. Theory

Our research is conducted within the insights provided by two sets of literature. The first body of literature originates from international relations and law, exploring why states choose to be bound by international human rights instruments¹. Empirically, this literature aims to decipher state 'socialisation' within the international human rights community. Normatively, it argues for desirable institutional features that encourage states to commit to human rights voluntarily. Building upon this foundation, we contemplate the extent to which this literature applies to Taiwan's special status—marked by permanent exclusion from international human rights institutions and the community. We also question whether this unique circumstance should influence the EU's approach to setting human rights standards.

The second body of literature addresses the misappropriation of rights rhetoric, particularly by the 'global right'². Initially, theorists in this realm identified phenomena similar to HRJ.

¹ Eg., Kai Alderson, 'Making Sense of State Socialization' (2001) 27 *Review of International Studies* <http://www.journals.cambridge.org/abstract_S0260210501004156> accessed 7 January 2024; Oona A Hathaway, 'Do Human Rights Treaties Make a Difference?' (2002) 111 *The Yale Law Journal* 1935; Ryan Goodman and Derek Jinks, 'How to Influence States: Socialization and International Human Rights Law' (2004) 54 *Duke Law Journal* 621; Ewan Harrison, 'State Socialization, International Norm Dynamics and the Liberal Peace' (2004) 41 *International Politics* 521; José E Alvarez, 'Do States Socialize?' (2005) 54 *Duke Law Journal* 961; Harold Hongju Koh, 'Internalization through Socialization' (2005) 54 *Duke Law Journal* 975; Oona A Hathaway, 'Why Do Countries Commit to Human Rights Treaties?' (2007) 51 *The Journal of Conflict Resolution* 588.

² Eg., Gráinne de Búrca and Katharine G Young, 'The (Mis)Appropriation of Human Rights by the New Global Right: An Introduction to the Symposium' (2023) 21 *International Journal of Constitutional Law* 205; Jayne Huckerby and Sarah Knuckey, 'Appropriation and the Rewriting of Rights' (2023) 21 *International Journal of Constitutional Law* 243; Farrah Ahmed, 'Constitutional Parasitism, Camouflage, and Pretense: Shaping

However, it becomes evident that this literature faces the challenge of making ideological judgments when evaluating human rights discourses. Perhaps not coincidentally, the literature emphasises the tension between family, religion, and sex equality. The distinct focus may imply a methodological difference between this body of literature and HRJ.

5. Preliminary Results

5.1 What HRJ Techniques We Have Identified (Task 1)

Through reviewing state HR reports, regulations, and press releases, we observed that the Taiwan government might adopt the following techniques of HRJ on migration:

- **Hierarchy of Rights:** The government prioritises A rights to counterbalance or undermine B rights.
- **Substitution of Stakeholders:** The government overlooks X stakeholders who are highly adversely impacted by a policy while emphasising Y stakeholders who are less affected.
- **Misappropriation of Concepts:** The government redefines the contents of rights and state obligations in a way that deviates from UN practices or authoritative interpretations.
- **Facade of Paternalism:** The government labels a restriction as a ‘benefit’ or ‘right’ (for the benefit of those who are restricted).
- **Confusion of Slighter Limitation:** The government suggests a less severe limitation is a ‘benefit’ or ‘right’.

For examples:

Categories of foreigners	HRJ examples	Techniques
Industrial and domestic migrant workers	♦ Deprivation of migrant workers’ right to work (i.e., no right to terminate employment and change employer unilaterally) and freedom of movement is counterbalanced by nationals ’ right to work.	Hierarchy of rights/Substitution of stakeholders

Citizenship through Subterfuge’ (2023) 21 International Journal of Constitutional Law 285; Başak Çalı and Esra Demir-Gürsel, ‘Continuity and Change in Human Rights Appropriation: The Case of Turkey’ (2023) 21 International Journal of Constitutional Law 266; Kapyra Kaoma, ‘The Interaction of Human Rights and Religion in Africa’s Sexuality Politics’ (2023) 21 International Journal of Constitutional Law 339; Kristina Stoeckl, ‘Traditional Values, Family, Homeschooling: The Role of Russia and the Russian Orthodox Church in Transnational Moral Conservative Networks and Their Efforts at Reshaping Human Rights’ (2023) 21 International Journal of Constitutional Law 224. See also the symposium: ‘Symposium: Misappropriation and Human Rights Implosion’ <<https://academy-humanrights.uni-koeln.de/en/news/past-events/symposium-misappropriation-and-human-rights-implosion>> accessed 7 January 2024.

	♦ The requirement of frequent health checks imposed on migrant workers is deemed a necessary means to protect nationals' right to health.	Hierarchy of rights/Substitution of stakeholders
	♦ The failure to protect foreign domestic workers (caregivers) with labour law is defended by workers' freedom of contract .	Misappropriation of concepts
	♦ Fixed-term contracts of migrant workers are said to protect workers' exit and 'leave' .	Misappropriation of concepts
Marriage immigrants	♦ Extraterritorial interview requirements for marriage immigrants to get a visa and resident permits are said to combat human trafficking and to realize foreigners' right to family reunions .	Façade of paternalism
Asylum seekers or stateless people	♦ The act of temporarily suspending deportation or transitioning to a third country as an ad hoc response to asylum requests in absence of asylum law is considered a way of fulfilling international human rights obligations under ICCPR .	Confusion of slighter limitation

5.2 How Our Observations Inform the Research Design in the Second Year (Task 2)

Firstly, based on the above observations, we suggest that helpful case studies of HRJ in the context of Taiwan may include:

- HRJ on combating human trafficking;
- HRJ on regulating migrant workers;
- HRJ on responding to asylum seekers and stateless people;
- HRJ on accepting marriage immigrants.

These cases also inform us about the spectrum of NGOs that should be invited to join the focus group. It should include NGOs focusing on migrant workers, asylum seekers, and marriage immigrants. Please note that our work in 2023 has led to a much more extensive survey scope, compared with our initial research proposal one year ago, to cover a wider variety of HRJ techniques.

Questions for the focus group will be formulated around their strategies to identify and resist HRJ on migration, if any. We hope to learn, from their perspectives, whether HRJ is any different from other pretexts for the government to pass the buck on human rights. We would also invite NGOs to share their experiences on the EU's role in their advocacy.

Secondly, we will further compare the above cases with two counterexamples below to illuminate the theoretical inquiries about:

1. peculiar features of HRJ on migration;
2. meaningful distinction between desirable HR justifications and undesirable ones, and
3. implications of undesirable HRJ on migration for EU external relationships and, more broadly, for the tension between democracy and human rights.

● **Counterexample One: Absence of HRJ Regarding Foreign Fishers**

We notice the curious absence of HRJ in the administration of fishers. The government tends not to justify the status of foreign fishers with human rights rhetoric. The tendency may be related to Taiwan's two-tier approach towards foreign fishers. That is, foreign fishers on Taiwanese vessels are classified into two categories according to the place of recruitment. Foreign fishers hired within Taiwan receive equal protection under labor laws, but those hired offshore are deemed outside the jurisdiction of Taiwanese law. Consequently, the government does not need to justify regulations on them.

As a general principle, a state's human rights obligations are mainly owed to people within its jurisdiction. Extra-territoriality, therefore, presents itself as an acute challenge to the human rights system aiming at universal coverage. Instead of (or, in addition to) manipulating human rights discourses with HRJ techniques, the state may manipulate the definition of the borderline to avoid its human rights obligations. More importantly for our purpose, the manipulation of territoriality is particularly problematic for migrants, who are, by definition, 'in-between' the border zone. The universality of human rights may easily become fragmented and the promise hollow. By comparing the manipulation of jurisdiction as opposed to HRJ techniques, we hope to gain insights into the general features of HRJ and the peculiarity of HRJ on migration.

Moreover, the EU has expressed deep concerns towards human rights standards on Taiwanese fishing vessels. During August 2023, we had a field trip to three fishing ports of different sizes in southern Taiwan. The field trip offered us an invaluable opportunity to understand the unions and organizations of foreign fishers. Our initial observation was that the EU's concern has been a lever for foreign fishers' advocates in Taiwan. Therefore, the case study of foreign fishers will highlight the EU's role in promoting human rights standards in a third country.

● **Counterexample Two: Positive Human Rights Obligations**

Positive human rights obligations require the state to adopt policies and actions to protect, promote, and fulfil human rights. Hence, on its face, justifying a policy based on a positive human rights obligation will look somewhat similar to HRJ. At the same time, failures to take necessary actions may appear neutral, measured by the status quo. For instance, Taiwan has refused to establish statutory labour standards for foreign caregivers hired by private households. This failure heightens the risk of forced labour, exploitation, and human trafficking. Nevertheless, before the absence of law can be marked as a deficit of human rights, we should be able to explain the exact distinction between a failure of human rights and occasions where the state rightly shies away from intervention.

By comparing the conditions and structure of positive human rights obligations, we hope to explore the distinction between undesirable HRJ and desirable state actions taken under human rights. This inquiry is also critical to explore the tension between democracy and human rights, particularly in the context of migration. In most countries (other than EU member states), migrants are, by default, outside the domain of democracy. The legitimacy of state power over foreigners is said to be based on the protection of human rights rather than their democratic participation. Should migrants’ rights be left unprotected due to HRJ, is the state power rendered illegitimate, or does it entail democratic deficits for migrants in any sense? These questions are particularly intriguing in light of positive human rights obligations in the context of migration. We, therefore, hope to contribute to the theoretical inquiry by comparing HRJ and positive HR obligations.

5.2 Schedule for Tasks 3-6

Tasks \ Time	Q1, 2024	Q2, 2024	Q3, 2024	Q4, 2024	Q1, 2025	Q2, 2025	Q3, 2025	Q4, 2025	Q1, 2026
T3: First civil society engagement		1 st focus group in Apr 2024							
T4: Analysing outputs				Analysis outcome by the year end					
T5: Second civil society engagement					2 nd focus group in Mar 2025				
T6: Synthesising all findings									
T7: Sharing reports with									
T8: Producing theme-specific reports and recommendations									

